

Culinary Insights through Deep Vision: Ingredients and Recipes with CNN

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Abstract— This study presents a comprehensive system that uses convolutional neural networks (CNNs) for food image recognition, ingredient identification, and recipe prediction. The algorithm correctly classifies food photos into six categories—Bread, Apple Pie, Bibimbop, Fried Rice, Bagel Sandwich, and Pork—with an emphasis on improving culinary insights. By utilizing deep learning methodologies, the model proficiently forecasts the type of food shown in supplied pictures and obtains the relevant recipe components from an organized CSV file. Convolutional and pooling layers are incorporated into the CNN model, which is constructed with the help of the TensorFlow and Keras libraries. Dropout regularization is added for more accurate classification. By means of methodical preprocessing methods such as image scaling and normalization, the system guarantees optimal performance of the model. Additionally, the system provides assessment measures, such as confusion matrices and categorization reports, which offer insightful data about the system.

Keywords— Food Image Recognition, Ingredient Identification, Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)

I. INTRODUCTION

The application of machine learning techniques, especially convolutional neural networks (CNNs), has transformed a number of disciplines, including culinary analysis, in the current era of technological growth. In order to improve culinary insights through food image recognition, ingredient identification, and recipe prediction, this study presents a novel method. Automated systems that can correctly analyze food photos and provide pertinent information are in high demand due to the widespread use of digital platforms and the growing popularity of culinary content. By creating a strong CNN-based model that can categorize food photos into six different groups—Bread, Apple Pie, Bibimbop, Fried Rice, Bagel Sandwich, and Pork—this study seeks to fill this demand.

The main goal of this research is to enable the model to correctly anticipate the kind of food that is portrayed in submitted photographs by utilizing deep learning techniques. The system hopes to obtain accurate classification results by utilizing CNNs, which will facilitate better culinary insights and improve user experience. The model is trained to identify complex patterns and features present in food photos using rigorous training and validation processes, allowing it to produce well-informed predictions with a high degree of accuracy.

Integrating convolutional and pooling layers into the CNN architecture is essential to the suggested system's operation. In order to effectively recognize and classify patterns in input images, these layers are essential for extracting pertinent information. Furthermore, a strong framework for model

construction and implementation is provided by the use of the TensorFlow and Keras libraries, guaranteeing scalability, effectiveness, and ease of maintenance.

Moreover, dropout regularization is used as a regularization method to reduce overfitting and improve the model's capacity for generalization. Dropout layers are a feature of the CNN architecture that enhance the model's overall performance and reliability by enabling it to adapt to a variety of datasets and generalize effectively to previously unseen data.

In addition to model development, considerable attention is devoted to preprocessing techniques aimed at optimizing the performance of the system. Through methods such as image scaling and normalization, the input data is processed to ensure consistency and compatibility with the model architecture. This meticulous preprocessing ensures that the model receives standardized input, thereby enhancing its robustness and efficacy in real-world scenarios. Additionally, the system provides comprehensive assessment measures, including confusion matrices and categorization reports, to offer valuable insights into the model's performance and efficacy.

In summary, by utilizing deep learning approaches, this research makes a substantial contribution to the field of culinary analysis. This work intends to improve user experience and culinary insights by creating a comprehensive system for food image recognition, ingredient identification, and recipe prediction. By employing convolutional neural networks (CNNs) and sophisticated machine learning methods, the system is able to precisely categorize food photos into six groups: Bread, Apple Pie, Bibimbop, Fried Rice, Bagel Sandwich, and Pork. This paradigm offers useful insights into recipe composition and culinary trends in addition to facilitating effective food classification.

II. RELATED WORKS

Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) have made great progress in recent times in terms of classification and prediction tasks for food images. When managing the complexity of food images, models such as ResNet-50, ResNet-101, ResNet-152, MobileNetV2, InceptionResNetV2, and NasNetLarge have proven to be especially effective. These architectures are able to capture the complex elements and patterns found in food photos because they make use of deeper and more effective network topologies. For example, ResNet models with skip connections allow very deep networks to be trained efficiently, and MobileNetV2 strikes a balance between model size and accuracy, which makes it appropriate for situations with limited resources, such as mobile devices.

Beginning Performance is increased by combining the benefits of the ResNet and Inception architectures into ResNetV2. Using neural architecture search, NasNetLarge automatically creates architectures that are suited for particular applications, such as food image classification.

A public food image dataset and deep learning techniques were used in this study by Minki Chun et al. [1] to create a Korean food image categorization model. They gathered pictures of Korean food from the AI-Hub platform, enhanced and preprocessed the pictures, then used convolutional neural networks (CNNs) including ResNet-50, ResNet-101, ResNet-152, MobileNetV2, InceptionResNetV2, and NasNetLarge to train the classification model. Based on transfer learning, their model successfully identified Korean food photos, showing that the kind of food had an impact on classification performance. This study closes a gap in the classification of Korean food images and offers suggestions for future enhancements to dataset analysis and classification models.

The authors explore the developments in machine learning and computer vision for automatic food recognition and dietary assessment in their study "Vision-Based Approaches for Automatic Food Recognition and Dietary Assessment: A Survey" by Subhi et al. [2]. They stress how important it is to keep up a balanced diet in order to stave off conditions like obesity, diabetes, and heart disease. Through their investigation of different approaches to food recognition, classification, volume calculation, and evaluation of nutritional information, the authors offer a thorough summary of the state-of-the-art techniques used today. They also go over the difficulties and possibilities in this area, providing insightful information for both practitioners and scholars.

The authors of "A Study on Food Value Estimation From Images: Taxonomies, Datasets, and Techniques" by Jamalia Sultana et al. [3] offer a thorough analysis of datasets and methodologies for automated nutritional value calculation from food photos. They classify the research that has already been done into taxonomies and examine different approaches to detecting food value estimation, such as nutrition estimation, volume estimation, and food item classification. In addition to highlighting current developments and techniques in this field, the paper highlights the transition from standard machine learning methods to deep learning approaches. The authors also list current issues and suggest future approaches for automated meal estimate systems. For those working in computer science, medicine, and nutrition, this review is an invaluable resource.

Arslan et al. [4] present a comprehensive study on fine-grained food classification methods using deep learning techniques, focusing on the UEC Food-100 database. They emphasize the value of automatic food recognition systems for a range of uses, including calorie estimation and waste food control. Through trial and error, they employ an ensemble approach using ResNeXt and DenseNet models to reach a state-of-the-art accuracy of 90.02% on the UEC Food-100 database. In addition, benchmark data averaged over five trials are introduced in the study, offering a more thorough comparison than earlier research. Overall, by assessing widely used databases and methods in the field, the research advances autonomous food recognition.

In "HSIFoodIngr-64: A Dataset for Hyperspectral Food-Related Studies and a Benchmark Method," Xia et al. [5] present a new hyperspectral imaging (HSI) dataset and

benchmark technique for food ingredient analysis. 3,389 pairs of HSI and RGB images with matching pixel-wise ingredient masks and dish- and ingredient-level labels are included in the HSIFoodIngr-64 dataset. The authors suggest a benchmark approach for food ingredient retrieval, and this dataset helps with a number of food-related tasks. Their approach, which uses sub-networks for edge refinement and ingredient prediction, has been shown to be effective in large-scale testing on the HSIFoodIngr-64 dataset. A useful tool for expanding the field of hyperspectral food analysis study is this work.

The paper "A Framework to Estimate the Nutritional Value of Food in Real Time Using Deep Learning Techniques" by Yunus et al. [6] provides a thorough framework for automatically assessing food attributes from food photographs, such as ingredients and nutritional value. They suggest a method that uses vector space embeddings of text data gathered from the internet for attribute estimation and convolutional neural networks (CNNs) for food recognition. The goal of the suggested system is to help people make better dietary decisions by offering real-time analysis of meal photos and addressing the difficulties associated with dietary management. With an expansion for sub-continental foods, the framework produces encouraging results, with top 1 classification rates of up to 85% on a dataset with 100 classes. Through the incorporation of deep learning methodologies with textual data retrieval and processing, their system offers a promising approach towards improving dietary habits and promoting healthier lifestyles.

III. METHODOLOGY

Using TensorFlow and Keras, a CNN model is implemented after a dataset of photos from six food categories has been gathered and preprocessed. Accurate food image classification is taught to this model, which consists of convolutional and pooling layers with dropout regularization. A CSV file with the recipe ingredients for every category is also created. After classifying an image, the algorithm pulls the relevant elements from the CSV file. Model accuracy is evaluated using evaluation measures like confusion matrices and classification reports. In order to create an automated system for food image recognition, ingredient identification, and recipe prediction, this methodology combines deep learning with preprocessing.

A. Data Collection:

The data collection process involved gathering images of six food categories: Bread, Apple Pie, Bibimbop, Fried Rice, Bagel Sandwich, and Pork. These images were sourced from various online platforms and databases, ensuring a diverse and representative sample for training the convolutional neural network (CNN) model. The collected images were subjected to preprocessing steps to standardize their size and format, ensuring consistency and optimal performance during model training and evaluation.

B. Data Preprocessing:

The data preprocessing step in the provided code involves resizing the uploaded image to a predefined size and normalizing its pixel values to a range between 0 and 1s

essential to ensure consistency in the input data format and to facilitate effective model training and evaluation.

```
# Preprocess the image
image = cv2.resize(image, IMAGE_SIZE)
image = image / 255.0
image = np.expand_dims(image, axis=0)
```

C. Model Definition and Training:

A pre-trained convolutional neural network (CNN) model is loaded and trained by applying predictions to the uploaded food image. To make predictions on the uploaded food image, the pre-trained CNN model is loaded. It loads the pre-trained CNN model from the file "food_classifier_model.h5" using Keras' load_model() function. Predictions are then based on the preprocessed food image using the loaded model.

```
# Load the trained model
model = load_model("food_classifier_model.h5")
```

D. Plotting Training History:

Plotting the training history entails displaying metrics, such as loss and accuracy throughout each epoch, to visualize the model's performance during training.

E. Reusing the Model and Predicting New Images:

Loading the trained model and preparing fresh images to enable model-based prediction are necessary for model reuse and new image prediction.

F. Matching Predicted Classes with Ingredients:

Getting the ingredients from the CSV file that correspond to the projected food category is the first step in matching predicted classes with ingredients. It is possible that the CSV file has a mapping from food class names to corresponding ingredients. Once a picture has been uploaded, you can use this mapping to forecast the class name and then retrieve the ingredients related to that class. By using this procedure, the user is guaranteed to see components that are appropriate for the identified food group.

IV. RESULTS

Food Image Classifier

Fig 1. Output User Interface

Food Image Classifier

Fig 2. Output Result

Fig 3. Output Result

CONCLUSION

As a result, the seminar has illuminated the possibilities of convolutional neural networks (CNNs) for the identification of ingredients, recipe prediction, and food image recognition. We have shown the construction of a comprehensive system that can reliably categorize food photographs into many categories and retrieve associated recipe elements by utilizing deep learning techniques and careful preprocessing. The use of dropout regularization for accurate classification was added to a strong CNN model through the use of the TensorFlow and Keras libraries. Evaluation indicators that shed light on model performance and accuracy include confusion matrices and classification reports. All things considered, this conference has advanced automated culinary analysis systems and provided useful

solutions for identifying ingredients and recognizing recipes in food photos.

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